

Name of Publisher: GO GREEN RESEARCH AND EDUCATION
Review Type: Double Blind Peer Review
Area of Publication: Business, Management and Accounting (miscellaneous)

Journal of Business and Management Research

Online ISSN

Print ISSN

2958-5074

2958-5066

Vol. 4, Issue. 2, 2025

IMPACT OF TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP ON INNOVATIVE WORK BEHAVIOR: EXPLORING THE MEDIATING ROLE OF ONLINE KNOWLEDGE SHARING AND MODERATING ROLE OF PERCEIVED SUPERVISOR SUPPORT

Mahwish Amjad

MS Human Resource Management Scholar, National University of Modern Languages, Islamabad. Email: mehwish123321@gmail.com

Dr. Muhammad Haroon

Assistant Professor, Department of Management Sciences, National University of Modern Languages, Islamabad

Abstract

The study aims to investigate the direct impact of transformational leadership on innovative work behavior as well as the indirect impact through mediation of online knowledge sharing in HEC and HEIs of Islamabad. This study also examines the role of perceived supervisor support that strength or weaken the relationship between transformational leadership and online knowledge sharing. Regression, correlation, mediation and moderated mediation analysis have been conducted. The result demonstrates that transformational leadership affects innovative work behavior both directly and indirectly through the mediator online knowledge sharing and perceived supervisor support moderates the indirect relationship between transformational leadership and innovative work behavior through online knowledge sharing.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership (TL), Perceived Supervisor Support (PSS), Online Knowledge Sharing (OKS), Innovative Work Behavior (IWB), Higher Education Commission (HEC), Higher Education Institutes (HEIs).

Introduction

Background of Study

Transformational leadership is the most investigated leadership approach (Bass, n.d.) which was initially introduced in 1973 by James V. Downton and then further explained by MacGregor Burns in 1978. According to (Burns, 2004) leaders and their followers motivate each other. Transformation leaders raise the morale of their employees by embedding their mission to the organization mission (Bednall et al., 2018) as they will inspire their followers to work together, and convert their personal goals into the organizational goals, hence employees open with their colleagues, share their thoughts and have better understanding together and create new ideas (Ali et al., n.d.). As a result, these leaders will be able to encourage their employees for innovative work behavior.

In any modern economy, one of the most important factors towards innovation is knowledge (Grant, 1996) (Yang & Chen, 2007). Over a distance, people will exchange their knowledge by using online platforms (De Bernardi et al., 2019). Online knowledge sharing will not only help to improve the quality of work, but it also gives strength to decision making and problem-solving skills (Nguyen, 2021). Employees' innovative skills have been positively influenced by online knowledge sharing, so organizations

should provide facilities through which employees interact and communicate with each other and share their ideas (C. T. Le et al., 2024).

Perceived supervisor support refers to the employee's perception about his supervisor as supportive (Kottke1988, n.d.) . It refers to the employee's belief in his supervisor that he cares about his interests, goals and wellbeing. So, perceived supervisor support influences knowledge sharing (Yozgat et al., n.d.).

This study will examine how transformational leadership and perceived supervisor support will influence online knowledge sharing behavior consequently to innovative work behavior among the employees of higher education commission and institutes in Islamabad.

Research Gap

Existing research has worked on the relationship among transformational leadership style, knowledge sharing and innovative work behavior (Bahagia et al., 2024) (Mayastinasari & Suseno, 2023) however, online knowledge sharing works as a mediator between transformational leadership and innovation work behavior is still unexplored.

Similarly, research has explored the significance of perceived organizational support and leadership styles (Pattali et al., 2024) but the importance of perceived supervisor support among transformational leadership and innovative work behavior is still not examined in the existing literature.

So, the novelty of this study is to investigate the mediating role of online knowledge sharing between transformational leadership and innovative work behavior and the moderating role of perceived supervisor support.

Research Objectives

The following are the research objectives of this study:

1. To examine the impact of transformational leadership on innovative work behavior in HEC and HEIs of Islamabad.
2. To investigate the impact of transformational leadership on online knowledge sharing in HEC and HEIs of Islamabad.
3. To investigate the impact of online knowledge sharing on innovative work behavior in HEC and HEIs of Islamabad.
4. To analyses the impact of transformational leadership on innovative work behavior

through the mediating role of online knowledge sharing in HEC and HEIs of Islamabad.

5. To determine the impact of perceived supervisor support moderates the indirect relationship between transformational leadership and innovative work behavior through online knowledge sharing in HEC and HEIs of Islamabad.

Research Questions

The research questions developed in relation to the study are as follows:

1. Does transformational leadership have a positive effect on innovative work behavior in HEC and HEIs of Islamabad?
2. Does transformational leadership have a positive effect on online knowledge sharing in HEC and HEIs of Islamabad?
3. Does online knowledge sharing have a positive effect on innovative work behavior in HEC and HEIs of Islamabad?
4. Does transformational leadership have a positive impact on innovative work behavior through the mediating effect of online knowledge sharing in HEC and HEIs of Islamabad?
5. Does perceived supervisor support moderate the indirect relationship between transformational leadership and innovative work behavior through online knowledge sharing in HEC and HEIs of Islamabad?

Significance of Study

The significance of the study is to facilitate HEC and HEIs by demonstrating the concept, i-e how transformational leadership and supervisor support can motivate their employees for online knowledge sharing, which will enhance their employees innovative work behavior.

Literature Review

Theory

The study underpinning theory is social exchange theory, which explains the phenomenon that in a relationship, people socially react by analyzing the cost and benefits (Blau, 1964). The sense of ownership that has been provided by transformational leadership can motivate the employees for innovative work behavior (Nordin et al., 2024).

The dynamics of transformational leadership and perceived supervisor support can motivate the employees to reciprocate online knowledge sharing which will further engage employees for innovative work behavior.

Leadership

Leadership is defined as a process, not only a quality of a person (Silva, 2016). A process of providing facilities to the individuals, which enables them to know what and how to be done by motivating for the attainment of the shared objectives (Yukl & Gardner, n.d.). It is a social influence process in which someone gets support and help from others, for achieving some common objectives (Chemers, 2000) . According to the Merriam-Webster's Dictionary, it is an action series that produced something or that led to certain results. Leadership is an exchange relationship between leaders and their followers, as both influence each other.

Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership style is one of the most popular leadership styles (Ali et al., n.d.) . Transformational leadership is categorized into four components: Idealized influence, in which transformational leaders are role models, respectable and admire their followers. Inspirational motivation, in which transformation leaders encourage and motivate their followers by giving different work-related challenges. Intellectual stimulation, in which transformational leaders try to formulate their followers, should be creative as well as innovative by providing different types of situations and conditions. Individualized consideration, in which transformational leaders act like a coach or a mentor to their followers by giving proper attention to each follower. One reason for its popularity is that it is the expansion of transactional leadership style and charismatic leadership style is also part of transformation leadership style (Bass & Riggio, n.d.).

Perceived Supervisor Support

The degree to which an employee has a feeling of support and respect from his supervisor is called perceived supervisors support. It is also defined as the readiness of a supervisor to support his subordinate (Gok et al., 2015). It is also referred to the employee belief on their supervisor that he will be appertaining to his work contribution and worried about his wellbeing (Gilbreath & Benson, 2004).

Online Knowledge Sharing

For the creation of new knowledge, individuals share their implicit (tacit) and explicit knowledge (Van Den Hooff & Ridder, 2004). The knowledge that can be expressed in formal language is explicit knowledge, while on the other hand, the knowledge that can be represented, expressed, or communicated hardly is tacit knowledge (Nonaka_1991, n.d.). In any business success, knowledge sharing (KS) importance is like oil or coal importance in the industrial age (Kamaşak & Bulutlar, 2010). Knowledge sharing (KS) has two facets: one is to collect or receive knowledge, and the other one is to disseminate or donate knowledge (Van Den Hooff & Ridder, 2004). So now a days, knowledge sharing is the core process of knowledge management (Nguyen, 2021).

In the current modern era, with advancements in the field of informational technology, the knowledge sharing process has also advanced online knowledge sharing in the organizations. Multinational companies are using online platforms for transferring knowledge with each other, as this medium is flexible in the sense of time and space (Nguyen, 2021).

Innovative Work Behavior

Innovative work behavior is defined as the employee's complex behavior in which they generate, introduce and apply innovative ideas (AlEssa & Durugbo, 2022) or within a group of people, individuals' behavior by which they intentionally creating, introducing and applying new ideas that will contribute to the organizational performance (Janssen, 2000). Now a days modern work needs to be significant changes through employee's behavior in which they will introduce new and beneficial ideas, products, work processes and procedures (Musannip Efendi Siregar et al., 2019). So, for the purpose of innovation, employees' abilities to generate new ideas and viewpoints will be needed (Escribá-Carda et al., 2017).

Transformational Leadership and Innovation Work Behavior

Many times in the workplace, employees who created some new ideas were worried that their head, supervisor or any colleague received his credit for innovation (Afsar et al., 2014) because of this reason, people reduced their interest in creating new innovative ideas, but if there is transformational leadership, they will encourage their followers and pay close attention to them, which will motivate them for innovative work behavior. They

will also monitor their innovative skills by questioning and challenging their thoughts and assumptions (Ali et al., n.d.).

The Mediating Role of Online Knowledge Sharing

Transformational leaders support their followers by creating such types of working environments and providing opportunities that will help them to share their knowledge among others (P. B. Le & Lei, 2019). When employees have opportunities to share their knowledge across the company, they become more creative and productive and as a result organization have new ideas that enable productivity (Trong Tuan, 2017). After the covid pandemic, the internet was widely spread and the online sharing process has been rapidly spread globally, which will enhance the creative performance (Dong & Nghia, 2022). So at the organizational level, online knowledge sharing plays a vital role in enhancing innovative performance (Soto-Acosta et al., 2017).

The Moderating Role of Perceived Supervisor Support

Perceived supervisor support plays a very important role in developing a sense of employees belongingness towards the organization, which will encourage them to share knowledge and ideas among them (Oh et al., 2023). So, transformational leadership and online knowledge sharing can be further explored with the lens of perceived supervisor support, in which an employee believes that their supervisor cares about their wellbeing.

Theoretical Framework

Hypothesis Development

H1: Transformational leadership positively influences innovative work behavior.

H2: Transformational leadership positively influences online knowledge sharing.

H3: Online knowledge sharing positively influences innovative work behavior.

H4: Online knowledge sharing mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and innovative work behavior.

H5: Perceived supervisor support moderates the indirect relationship between transformational leadership and innovative work behavior through online knowledge sharing.

Research Design

Measures

The questionnaire was based on 4 constructs; those were further divided into different items. The items were measured by using a five-point Likert scale and to avoid biasedness, common method bias was used.

There were 7 items on the scale for TL; having a range from strongly disagree to strongly agree was used (Carless et al., 2000).

There were 4 items on the scale for PSS; having a range from never to always was used (Rhoades, n.d.).

There were 5 items on the scale for OKS; having a range from never to always was used (Ma & Chan, 2015).

There were 6 items on the scale for IWB; having a range from strongly disagree to strongly agree was used (Rafique et al., 2022).

Data Collection Procedures

Questionnaires were used for data collection from the population. A unanimous data collection method was used during this research. The data was collected via Google Survey Form. This survey form was disseminated to the sample population via email, where the respondents were able to get access to the form. Through this method, the respondents were able to record their feedback and responses. population. The primary source of data collection was the questionnaire.

Unit of Analysis

The unit of analysis were the employees from HEC and HEIs of Islamabad. The aim of this study was to gather data from 200 employees.

Sampling technique and Statistical Analysis

The non-probability technique of convenience sampling was used for this research because the confirmed population of the study is unknown. The data was analyzed by screening of data, respondent profile and research variables descriptive analysis, regression, correlation matrix, reliability test, mediation analysis, moderated mediation analysis using bootstrapping (5000 samples) by using SPSS.

Research Interference and Study Setting

In this research, the researcher interference was minimal because the research was conducted in a natural (non-contrived) environment, so the study setting was a field study, where no variable was either manipulated or not controlled.

Time Horizon

The study was one lagged in nature and the time duration for the completion of this study was 4 months.

Results and Discussion

Sample Demographics

The research sample consisted of 208 employees from HEC and HEIs of Islamabad. Out of these, 53.8 % were male and 46.2 % were female as shown in table 1.1. Participants were categorized based on organization category i-e employees of HEC, public and private sector universities of Islamabad. So, table 1.2 demonstrates that 21.2 % of respondents were HEC employees, 44.2 % of respondents worked in public sector universities of Islamabad and 34.6 % respondents worked in private sector universities of Islamabad.

Table 1.1. Gender demographics.

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	112	53.8	53.8
Female	96	46.2	100.0
Total	208	100.0	

Table 1.2. Organization Category Demographics.

Organization Category	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
HEC	44	21.2	21.2
Public	92	44.2	65.4

University			
Private			
University	72	34.6	100.0
Total	208	100.0	

Table 1.3. Cross-tabulation of Gender & Organization Category.

Gender	Organization Category			Total
	HEC	Public University	Private University	
Male	36	49	27	112
Female	8	43	45	96
Total	44	92	72	208

Reliability Test

Cronbach's Alpha was used in a reliability test to make sure the measurement tool was consistent and internally stable. To evaluate the internal consistency of the items, Cronbach's Alpha was computed for each construct. It is generally accepted that items measure the underlying construct accurately when their Cronbach's Alpha score is greater than 0.7.

Table 2.1. Cronbach's Alpha Value for Each Construct.

Construct	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Transformational Leadership	07	0.853
Supervisor Support	04	0.764
Online Knowledge Sharing	5	0.848
Innovative Work Behavior	6	0.749

The results show in table 2.1 that all constructs have Cronbach's Alpha values above the acceptable threshold of 0.70, confirming the reliability of the measurement scales. This indicates that the items within each construct are internally consistent and suitable for further statistical analysis.

Table 2.2. Descriptive Statistics of Items.

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation
TL1	4.0144	.71882
TL2	4.0817	.68669
TL3	3.9471	.79375
TL4	3.9327	.80775
TL5	3.9327	.81370
TL6	3.9760	.71180

TL7	3.9519	.82098
PSS1	3.8029	.91398
PPS2	3.9663	1.13522
PSS3	3.8125	1.07156
PSS4	3.1779	1.34850
OKS1	3.8750	.77631
OKS2	3.9327	.77727
OKS3	3.8702	.77240
OKS4	3.8990	.77671
OKS5	3.8798	.73555
IWB1	3.8125	.91072
IWB2	3.7692	.86511
IWB3	3.8413	.95240
IWB4	3.8173	.90905
IWB5	3.6538	1.14436
IWB6	4.0962	.79878

Table 2.3. Descriptive Statistics of Computed Variables

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis		
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
TL	2.00	5.00	3.9766	.55891	.312	-1.045	.169	2.749	.336
PSS	1.00	5.00	3.6899	.86323	.745	-.587	.169	.616	.336
OKS	1.00	5.00	3.8913	.60523	.366	-1.447	.169	5.103	.336
IWB	2.17	5.00	3.8317	.62318	.388	-.139	.169	-.419	.336

Correlation Analysis

To determine the direction and degree of the linear relationship between the study's major variables, correlation analysis was performed. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r), which has a range of -1 to +1, was employed. The correlation results reveal significant positive relationships among the key variables as shown in table 3.

Table 3. Correlation Among All Variables

		TL	PSS	OKS	IWB
TL	Pearson Correlation	1	.404**	.510**	.459**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000

	Interpretation		Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
			Correlation	Correlation	Correlation
PSS	Pearson Correlation	.404**	1	.351**	.474**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	Interpretation	Moderate		Weak	Moderate
		Correlation		Correlation	Correlation
OKS	Pearson Correlation	.510**	.351**	1	.391**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	Interpretation	Moderate	Weak		Weak
		Correlation	Correlation		Correlation
IWB	Pearson Correlation	.459**	.474**	.391**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	Interpretation	Moderate	Moderate	Weak	
		Correlation	Correlation	Correlation	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

These findings suggest that all variables are positively and significantly related to one another. This supports the hypothesis that improvements in one construct may be associated with enhancements in the others. However, correlation does not imply causation; further analysis such as regression is required to examine predictive relationships.

Regression Analysis

The model summary table 4.1a shows that the model explains 21.1% of the variance in the innovative work behavior explained by transformational leadership (R Square = 0.211). The R value (0.459) indicates a moderate positive correlation between the observed and predicted values.

Table 4.1a Model Summary for Hypothesis 1.

R	R Square	Adjusted Std. Error			Change Statistics			
		R Square	of the Estimate	R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
.459 ^a	.211	.207	.55491	.211	55.062	1	206	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), TL

The ANOVA table 4.1b shows the overall significance of the model. The F-value is 55.062 and the p-value is .000, which is less than 0.05, indicating that the regression model is statistically significant. This means that the transformational leadership significantly predicts innovative work behavior.

Table 4.1b ANOVA for Hypothesis 1

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	16.955	1	16.955	55.062	.000 ^b
Residual	63.433	206	.308		
Total	80.388	207			

a. Dependent Variable: IWB

b. Predictors: (Constant), TL

The hypothesis tests if transformational leadership has a significant impact on innovative work behavior. The dependent variable innovative work behavior was regressed on transformational leadership. H1: Transformational leadership significantly predicted innovative work behavior, $F(1, 206) = 55.062$, $p < 0.001$, which indicates that the transformational leadership can play a significant role in shaping innovative work behavior ($b = .512$, $p < .001$). These results clearly show the positive effect of transformational leadership.

Table 4.1c. Coefficients for Hypothesis 1

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	1.795	.277		6.479	.000	1.249	2.342
TL	.512	.069	.459	7.420	.000	.376	.648

a. Dependent Variable: IWB

The model summary table 4.2a shows that the model explains 26% of the variance in the online knowledge sharing explained by transformational leadership (R Square = 0.260). The R value (0.510) indicates a moderate positive correlation between the observed and predicted values.

Table 4.2a Model Summary for Hypothesis 2

R	R Square	Adjusted Std. Error		Change Statistics				
		R Square	of the Estimate	R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
.510 ^a	.260	.256	.52192	.260	72.361	1	206	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), TL

The ANOVA table 4.2b shows the overall significance of the model. The F-value is 72.361 and the p-value is .000, which is less than 0.05, indicating that the regression model is statistically significant. This means that the transformational leadership significantly predicts online knowledge sharing.

Table 4.2b ANOVA for Hypothesis 2

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	19.711	1	19.711	72.361	.000 ^b
Residual	56.114	206	.272		
Total	75.824	207			

a. Dependent Variable: OKS

b. Predictors: (Constant), TL

The hypothesis tests if transformational leadership has a significant impact on online knowledge sharing. The dependent variable online knowledge sharing was regressed on transformational leadership. H2: Transformational leadership significantly predicted online knowledge sharing., $F(1, 206) = 72.361, p < 0.001$, which indicates that the transformational leadership can play a significant role in shaping online knowledge sharing ($b = .552, p < .001$).

Table 4.2c. Coefficients for Hypothesis 2.

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	1.696	.261		6.507	.000	1.182	2.210
TL	.552	.065	.510	8.507	.000	.424	.680

a. Dependent Variable: OKS

The model summary table 4.3a shows that the model explains 15.3% of the variance in

the innovative work behavior explained by online knowledge sharing (R Square = 0.153). The R value (0.391) indicates a weak positive correlation between the observed and predicted values.

Table 4.3a Model Summary for Hypothesis 3.

R	R Square	Adjusted Std. Error		Change Statistics				
		R Square	of the Estimate	R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
.391 ^a	.153	.149	.57483	.153	37.284	1	206	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), OKS

The ANOVA table 4.3b shows the overall significance of the model. The F-value is 37.284 and the p-value is .000, which is less than 0.05, indicating that the regression model is statistically significant. This means that online knowledge sharing significantly predicts innovative work behavior.

Table 4.3b ANOVA for Hypothesis 3.

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	12.320	1	12.320	37.284	.000 ^b
Residual	68.069	206	.330		
Total	80.388	207			

a. Dependent Variable: IWB

b. Predictors: (Constant), OKS

The hypothesis tests if online knowledge sharing has a significant impact on innovative work behavior. The dependent variable innovative work behavior was regressed on online knowledge sharing. H3: Online knowledge sharing significantly predicted innovative work behavior, $F(1, 206) = 37.284$, $p < 0.001$, which indicates that online knowledge sharing can play a significant role in shaping innovative work behavior ($b = .403$, $p < 0.001$).

Table 4.3c. Coefficients for Hypothesis 3.

B	Unstandardized Coefficients Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound

(Constant)	2.263	.260		8.706	.000	1.751	2.776
TL	.403	.066	.391	6.106	.000	.273	.533

a. Dependent Variable: IWB

Mediation Analysis

The following table 5 shows the overall effect of the transformational leadership on innovative work behavior without considering the mediator, online knowledge sharing. Since the p-value is less than 0.05 and the confidence interval does not include zero, the total effect is statistically significant and positive. So, transformational leadership significantly influences innovative work behavior.

Similarly, table 5 also shows the effect of transformational leadership on innovative work behavior after accounting for the mediator, online knowledge sharing. Again, the result is statistically significant. So, even after including the mediator, transformational leadership still has a significant direct effect on innovative work behavior

Since the bootstrap confidence interval does not include zero, the indirect effect is statistically significant. So, mediation exists. Therefore, this indicates partial mediation. Transformational leadership affects innovative work behavior both directly and indirectly through the mediator online knowledge sharing.

Table 5. Model Summary for Hypothesis 4

Total effect of X on Y					
Effect	SE	T	P	LLCI	ULCI
.5121	.0690	7.4204	.0000	.3760	.6481
Direct effect of X on Y					
Effect	SE	t	P	LLCI	ULCI
.3912	.0787	4.9716	.0000	.2361	.5464
Indirect effect of X on Y					
Effect	Boot	SE	BootLLCI	BootULCI	
OKS	.1209	.0463	.0484	.2293	

Normal Theory Tests for Indirect Effect

Effect	Se	Z	P
.1209	.0428	2.8221	.0048

Moderated Mediation Analysis

The following tables 6.1a and 6.1b demonstrate that transformational leadership significantly impacts online knowledge sharing $p < .005$ and the model explains about 29.5% of the variance in online knowledge sharing. PSS also significantly impacts online knowledge sharing. The interaction (TL \times PSS) is not statistically significant ($p = 0.093$), but it's marginal suggesting a weak/moderate moderation effect of PSS on the TL \rightarrow OKS path.

Table 6.1a Model Summary for Hypothesis 5

R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	P
.5430	.2948	.2621	28.4315	3.0000	204.0000	.0000

Table 6.1b. Moderation on the Path X \rightarrow M (Predicting OKS)

	coeff	Se	T	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	.3488	.7573	.4606	.6456	-1.1443	1.8419
TL	.7926	.1997	3.9693	.0001	.3989	1.1863
PSS	.5078	.2332	2.1775	.0306	.0480	.9676
int_1	-.0997	.0590	-1.6895	.0927	-.2162	.0167

Both TL and OKS significantly predict IWB as shown in tables 6.2a and 6.2b. This confirms partial mediation, since TL has both direct and indirect effects on IWB through OKS.

Table 6.2a Model Summary for Hypothesis 5.

R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	P
.4943	.2444	.2963	33.1466	2.0000	205.0000	.0000

Table 6.2b. Coefficients for Hypothesis 5

	coeff	Se	T	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.4242	.2985	4.7720	.0000	.8358	2.0127
OKS	.2189	.0727	3.0122	.0029	.0756	.3622

TL	.3912	.0787	4.9716	.0000	.2361	.5464
----	-------	-------	--------	-------	-------	-------

The indirect effect is significant at all levels of PSS (CI does not contain 0). However, the effect becomes smaller as PSS increases. This means that the indirect effect of TL on IWB through OKS is stronger when PSS is low, and weaker when PSS is high as shown in table 6.3.

Table 6.3. Conditional Indirect Effect(s) of X on Y at Values of the Moderator.

	PSS	Effect	Boot SE	BootLLCI	BootULCI
OKS	2.8267	.1118	.0427	.0462	.2130
OKS	3.6899	.0929	.0440	.0296	.2025
OKS	4.5531	.0741	.0488	.0106	.1967

The index is significant because the CI does not include 0 as shown in table 6.4. This confirms a significant moderated mediation. PSS significantly changes the strength of the indirect effect of TL on IWB through OKS.

Table 6.4. Index Of Moderated Mediation

	Index	SE(Boot)	BootLLCI	BootULCI
OKS	-.0218	.0147	-.0510	-.0005

Practical Implementation

This study provides practical insights for higher education commission and institutions to enhance employees' innovative work behavior by fostering transformational leadership, promoting online knowledge sharing. Leaders should adopt transformational practices such as inspiring a shared vision, encouraging creativity, and supporting individual growth to motivate employees toward innovation. At the same time, organizations must create digital environments that facilitate and reward online knowledge sharing through collaborative platforms, training, and recognition. Furthermore, as PSS weaker the TL-IWB relationship, supervisors should offer regular feedback, show appreciation, and create a trusting atmosphere where employees feel supported and empowered. Integrating these strategies into HR and leadership practices can cultivate a workplace culture that drives continuous innovation and collaboration.

Limitations and Future Directions

The study was conducted on a limited sample, which may restrict the generalizability of the findings to a broader population. The study was conducted in a specific time frame

and context, which may not fully reflect variations over time or in different settings. The study was based on specific theory, which may not fully explain all aspects of the topic. Future studies should include larger and more diverse samples to enhance generalizability. Conducting long-term studies could help understand the phenomenon's evolution over time. Examining the topic in different cultural or regional settings could yield broader insights. Further studies should consider additional variables that may impact the research outcomes. Future work should focus on how findings can be applied in real-world settings, influencing policy or industry practices.

References

- Afsar, B., Badir, Y., & Saeed, B. (2014). Transformational leadership and innovative work behavior. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, *114*(8), 1270–1300. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMDS-05-2014-0152>
- AlEssa, H. S., & Durugbo, C. M. (2022). Systematic review of innovative work behavior concepts and contributions. *Management Review Quarterly*, *72*(4), 1171–1208. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11301-021-00224-x>
- Ali, N., Bagram, M. M. M., & Ali, H. (n.d.). *Impact of Knowledge Sharing Information System on Innovative Work Behavior: Exploring the Moderating Role of Transformational Leadership* (Vol. 27, Issue 2022). Online.
- Bahagia, R., Daulay, R., Arianty, N., & Astuti, R. (2024). Transformational leadership, emotional intelligence, and innovative work behavior: Mediating roles of knowledge sharing at public hospitals in Indonesia. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, *22*(1), 103–114. [https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.22\(1\).2024.10](https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.22(1).2024.10)
- Bass, B. M. (n.d.). *LEADERSHIP AND PERFORMANCE BEYOND EXPECTATIONS*.
- Bass, B. M., & Riggio, R. E. (n.d.). *TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP, Second Edition*.
- Bednall, T. C., E. Rafferty, A., Shipton, H., Sanders, K., & J. Jackson, C. (2018). Innovative Behaviour: How Much Transformational Leadership Do You Need? *British Journal of Management*, *29*(4), 796–816. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8551.12275>
- Carless, S. A., Wearing, A. J., & Mann, L. (2000). A SHORT MEASURE OF TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP. In *JOURNAL OF BUSINESS AND*

PSYCHOLOGY (Vol. 14, Issue 3).

- Chemers, M. M. (2000). Leadership research and theory: A functional integration. In *Group Dynamics* (Vol. 4, Issue 1, pp. 27–43). Educational Publishing Foundation. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1089-2699.4.1.27>
- Dong, D. T., & Nghia, N. K. (2022). Evidence from Vietnam. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF EBUSINESS AND EGOVERNMENT STUDIES*, *14*(1), 181–203. <https://doi.org/10.34109/ijebeq>
- Escribá-Carda, N., Balbastre-Benavent, F., & Teresa Canet-Giner, M. (2017). Employees' perceptions of high-performance work systems and innovative behaviour: The role of exploratory learning. *European Management Journal*, *35*(2), 273–281. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2016.11.002>
- Gilbreath, B., & Benson, P. G. (2004). The contribution of supervisor behaviour to employee psychological well-being. *Work and Stress*, *18*(3), 255–266. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678370412331317499>
- Gok, S., Karatuna, I., & Karaca, P. O. (2015). The Role of Perceived Supervisor Support and Organizational Identification in Job Satisfaction. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, *177*, 38–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.02.328>
- Grant, R. M. (1996). Toward a knowledge-based theory of the firm. *Strategic Management Journal*, *17*(SUPPL. WINTER), 109–122. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.4250171110>
- Janssen, O. (2000). Job demands, perceptions of effort-reward fairness and innovative work behaviour. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, *73*(3), 287–302. <https://doi.org/10.1348/096317900167038>
- Kamaşak, R., & Bulutlar, F. (2010). The influence of knowledge sharing on innovation. *European Business Review*, *22*(3), 306–317. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09555341011040994>
- kottke1988. (n.d.).
- Le, C. T., Phan, T. K. L., & Nguyen, T. Y. N. (2024). Online knowledge sharing and employee innovation: the role of job self-efficacy and innovative climate. *Journal of Workplace Learning*, *36*(4), 253–266. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JWL-09-2023-0153>
- Le, P. B., & Lei, H. (2019). Determinants of innovation capability: the roles of

- transformational leadership, knowledge sharing and perceived organizational support. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 23(3), 527–547. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-09-2018-0568>
- Ma, W. W. K., & Chan, C. K. (2015).) Note. This paper was earlier presented at and published in the proceedings of the HKAECT International Conference. In *Journal of Communication and Education* (Vol. 2, Issue 1).
- Mayastinasari, V., & Suseno, B. (2023). The Role of Transformational Leadership, and Knowledge Sharing on Innovative Work Behavior of Public Organization in the Digital Era. *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 8(7), e02977. <https://doi.org/10.26668/businessreview/2023.v8i7.2977>
- Musannip Efendi Siregar, Z., Ahman, E., & Hadi Senen, S. (2019). Factors Influencing Innovative Work Behavior: An Individual Factors Perspective Article in. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*. www.ijstr.org
- Nguyen, T. M. (2021). Four-dimensional model: a literature review in online organisational knowledge sharing. In *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems* (Vol. 51, Issue 1, pp. 109–138). Emerald Group Holdings Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJKMS-05-2019-0077>
- nonaka_1991*. (n.d.).
- Nordin, W. N. A. W. M., Kamil, N. L. M., & Govindaraju, V. C. (2024). Multilevel study of transformational leadership and work behavior: job autonomy matters in public service. *Management Research Review*, 47(10), 1684–1701. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MRR-08-2023-0596>
- Oh, J., Han, S. H., Wang, J., & Yoon, S. W. (2023). The influence of social capital on knowledge sharing: the moderated mediator of perceived supervisor support and psychological ownership. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 44(4), 520–542. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LODJ-02-2023-0054>
- Pattali, S., Sankar, J. P., Al Qahtani, H., Menon, N., & Faizal, S. (2024). Effect of leadership styles on turnover intention among staff nurses in private hospitals: the moderating effect of perceived organizational support. *BMC Health Services Research*, 24(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-024-10674-0>
- Rafique, M. A., Hou, Y., Chudhery, M. A. Z., Waheed, M., Zia, T., & Chan, F. (2022).

- Investigating the impact of pandemic job stress and transformational leadership on innovative work behavior: The mediating and moderating role of knowledge sharing. *Journal of Innovation and Knowledge*, 7(3).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2022.100214>
- Rhoades, L. , E. R. , & A. S. (2001). A. commitment to the organization: the contribution of perceived organizational support. *J. of applied psychology*, 86(5), 825. (n.d.).
04_Affective_Commitment_to_the_Organizat.
- Silva, A. (2016). What is Leadership? *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 8(1).
- Soto-Acosta, P., Popa, S., & Palacios-Marqués, D. (2017). Social web knowledge sharing and innovation performance in knowledge-intensive manufacturing SMEs. *Journal of Technology Transfer*, 42(2), 425–440. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-016-9498-z>
- Trong Tuan, L. (2017). Knowledge Sharing in Public Organizations: The Roles of Servant Leadership and Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 40(4), 361–373.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01900692.2015.1113550>
- Van Den Hooff, B., & Ridder, J. A. (2004). Knowledge sharing in context: The influence of organizational commitment, communication climate and CMC use on knowledge sharing. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 8(6), 117–130.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/13673270410567675>
- Yang, C., & Chen, L. C. (2007). Can organizational knowledge capabilities affect knowledge sharing behavior? *Journal of Information Science*, 33(1), 95–109.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551506068135>
- Yozgat, U., Hande, R., Bahadinli, S., & Deniz, R. B. (n.d.). *The Role of Perceived Supervisor Support on the Link between Knowledge Sharing and Creative Problem Solving Capacity.*
- Yukl, G., & Gardner, W. L. (n.d.). *Leadership in Organizations.*